

ha⁻¹), saving nearly 57% labor compared with hand weeding (127 person-days ha⁻¹). It also had better weed control efficiency. Though herbicide use produced comparable rice yield, their use may be limited to the cropped field because of adverse effects on the environment. The Phulbani dryland weeder was cheap, making it very popular among

Orissa farmers. It was concluded that the Phulbani dryland weeder should be recommended for weeding all crops. It can be used for crust breaking and for harvesting groundnut and potato.

Reference

OUAT Dryland Research Station. 2000. Annual report. Phulbani, Orissa (India): OUAT.

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Adoption of preharvest interval in rice cultivation

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The problem of pesticide residues in food, especially in cereals, fruits, and vegetables, has spurred the implementation of certain policy measures to minimize this problem. It is well recognized that if pesticide is applied too close to harvesting date, toxic substances are probably retained in consumer food. In Sri Lanka, this situation can be prevented by adhering to a preharvest interval (PHI), which is mandated by law. The preharvest interval is a period that usually varies from 7 to 21 d, depending on the toxicity of the pesticides. The Pesticide Act of 1980 prohibits the harvesting or selling of any food crop treated with pesticide until the prescribed PHI is employed. Highly toxic pesticides have a longer PHI and less toxic ones have a shorter PHI. The recommended PHI is stated on the label of the pesticide bottle. Further, these PHIs are also disseminated through the country's extension system.

To identify how the PHI is practically applied in rice cultivation, a study was conducted in the low-country,

dry zone of Sri Lanka. Two Grama Niladhari divisions (village-level administrative divisions where local extension workers are assigned), Koggala and Siyambalagaswila South in the Ambalantota agrarian service center area in Hambantota District, were selected for the study. Sixty farmers were randomly chosen for the field investigation. Farm visits and farmer interviews were conducted at the end of the 1997-98 maha season (the major rice

cultivation season that starts in October and ends in February).

Farmers were asked what was the last pesticide they applied in the field and how many days after pesticide application was the crop harvested. The results showed that farmers did not adhere to the PHI (days are calculated as averages for farmers who used a particular insecticide) (see figure). For BPMC, Bassa, and Becarb, the recommended PHI is 14 d, but farmers harvested their crops just 4-7 d after

Difference between what is recommended and what is practiced.

pesticide application. Further investigation revealed that BPMC was used to control brown planthopper (BPH, *Nilaparvata lugens*) attack, which occurred at the milking stage. Farmers were compelled to use BPMC, leading

to higher levels of BPMC residues in the rice grain. However, it was not clear whether BPH infestation close to harvest will cause a serious yield loss. This highlights the need for more farmer education programs that will

raise awareness about the interaction between pest infestation and use of pesticides. Increased awareness on this could reduce unnecessary spraying of pesticides.

Input use and socioeconomic characteristics of rice farmers: gender dimensions and implications for smallholder agriculture in Nigeria

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The topic “women in development” has become increasingly prominent in the literature on rural development and the phrase “women component” has become a popular catchword among policymakers in recent years. As increasing attention is paid to world poverty, food shortages, and overpopulation, the important role of women can no longer be ignored. Researchers and practitioners are discovering that not only do women make up a large proportion of the world’s poor, they are also the main provider of food and basic necessities for their families. These discoveries have had major implications in academic research and policymaking. In addition, the positive contributions made by women to their communities as well as to their national economies have been undervalued. In many instances, women have been viewed as a drain on scarce resources rather than an asset in economic development. This study examined the gender dimensions of the impact of input use and socioeconomic characteristics of farmers on their level of efficiency in rice cultivation in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

The study focused mainly on small-scale farmers cultivating less than 5 ha of land. Representative samples of equal numbers (40) of respondents were randomly selected in two villages from two local government areas in the state. The analytical approach involved descriptive statistics, and the estimation of a stochastic frontier model through maximum likelihood estimation procedure.

The stochastic frontier model specified output (Y) as a function of inputs (X) and a disturbance term (ε): $Y_{ij} = f(X_{1j} + X_{2j} + \dots + X_{nj}, A; \varepsilon)$, where Y_i is output by farmer i , X_{ij} is input j of

n inputs, and A is a vector of parameters (“ μ ”). The disturbance term in stochastic frontier models consists of two components, $\varepsilon_i = V_i - U_i$, where $V_i \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$ and U_i is a one-sided error term. The one-sided term, U_i , represents technical inefficiency (TI) relative to the stochastic frontier. If $U_i = 0$, production lies on the stochastic frontier and production is technically efficient; if $U_i > 0$, production lies below the frontier and is inefficient.

Table 1 compares the male and female respondents in terms of their use of farm inputs. It can be noted that there was no

Table 1. Mean values of input use per hectare and socioeconomic characteristics of farmers.

Input/characteristic	Aggregate	Male	Female
Input			
Farm size (ha)	3.15	4.74	1.48
Family labor (person-days)	125.99	112.75	130.55
Hired labor (person-days)	25.81	25.75	25.67
Traction (h)	4.77	4.91	4.32
Agrochemicals (L)	3.21	2.43	5.78
Seed (kg)	99.88	67.31	90.46
Fertilizer (kg)	76.71	95.62	114.02
Yield (t)	1.8	1.1	0.39
Farmer characteristics			
Age (y)	40.33	45.62	34.77
Education (y)	6.81	8.00	5.55
Contact with extensive agents (No)	9.41	9.95	8.85
Estimated farm income (Naira)	73,2523.60	43,522.80	73,2523.60
Farming experience (y)	22.62	24.91	20.22
Household size (no.)	6.76	8.23	5.22